

Core-Shell Fe₃O₄@Au Nanorod-Loaded Gels for Tunable and Anisotropic Magneto- and Photo- Thermia

Mikel Rincón-Iglesias,[†] Irati Rodrigo,^{†,‡,#} Leixuri B. Berganza,[†] Esraa Samy Abu Serea,[†]
Fernando Plazaola,[‡] Senentxu Lanceros-Méndez,^{†,§} Erlantz Lizundia,^{†,‡*} Javier Reguera^{†*}

[†] BCMaterials, Basque Center for Materials, Applications, and Nanostructures, UPV/EHU
Science Park, 48940 Leioa, Spain.

[‡] Elektrizitatea eta Elektronika Saila, Facultad de Ciencia y Tecnología, Universidad del País
Vasco/Euskal Herriko Unibertsitatea (UPV/EHU), 48940 Leioa, Spain

[§] Ikerbasque Basque Foundation for Science Bilbao 48009, Spain

[‡] Life Cycle Thinking Group, Department of Graphic Design and Engineering Projects.
University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU), Plaza Ingeniero Torres Quevedo 1, 48013
Bilbao, Biscay, Spain

[#] Dr. Irati Rodrigo's current address: Department of Bioengineering, University of California
Berkeley, Berkeley 94720-762, USA

*: Corresponding authors: erlantz.liizundia@ehu.eus; javier.reguera@bcmaterials.net

ABSTRACT

Hyperthermia therapeutic treatments require improved multifunctional materials with tunable synergetic properties. Here we report on the synthesis of $\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4@Au$ core-shell nanorods and their subsequent incorporation into an agarose hydrogel to obtain anisotropic magnetic and optical properties for magneto- and photo-thermal anisotropic transductions. Highly monodisperse ferrimagnetic Fe_3O_4 nanorods with tunable size were synthesized by a solvothermal method by varying the amount of hexadecylamine capping ligand. A gold shell was coated onto Fe_3O_4 nanorods by the intermediate formation of core-satellite structures and a subsequent controlled growth process, leading to an optical response variation from the visible to the near IR region. The nanorods were oriented within an agarose hydrogel to fabricate free-standing anisotropic materials, providing a proof of concept for the applicability of these materials for anisotropic magneto- and photo-thermia applications. The strongly gelling upon cooling and shear-thinning behavior of agarose enables the fabrication of magnetically active continuous hydrogel filaments upon injection. These developed multifunctional nanohybrid materials represent a base for advanced sensing, biomedical, or actuator applications with an anisotropic response.

Keywords: magnetic nanorods; anisotropy; plasmonic; core-shell; agarose; hydrogels; injectable; magnetothermia.

INTRODUCTION

Hybrid nanomaterials have received increasing attention in recent years given their high versatility and tunability for specific applications.¹⁻³ Upon the combination of materials with different structures and functionalities, a hybrid material could be obtained with multifunctional features enabling diverse tasks to be performed simultaneously.⁴ In this scope, since they were firstly reported in the early 1990s, hybrid core-shell nanoparticles offer unique characteristics including high thermal/chemical stabilities, low toxicity, or improved solubility.⁵ These nanoparticles generally consist of a core (inner material) and a shell (outer layer material).⁵ Generally, concentric core-shell nanoparticles are the most commonly reported hybrid nanomaterials, where a spherical core is coated by a shell of a different material. The introduction of different shapes represents a further step as it results in novel functionalities based on the anisotropic characteristics and functional response. Thus, anisotropic nanoparticles having asymmetric axes are particularly attractive as they show varying and controlled physical properties along the different orientations.⁶

In this context, Au nanorods (Au NRs) are considered a good example, where two distinct localized surface plasmon resonances (LSPR) can be obtained in the longitudinal and transverse directions.⁷ In a somehow similar way, Au nanoshells offer also two plasmonic dipolar modes from hybridization of a sphere and a cavity.⁸ The merger of both, to form rod-shaped nanoshell, gives rise to more complex plasmonic modes with higher tunability and large local field intensity enhancements.⁹ Combining a Au NR shell with a magnetic core can result in optically and magnetically active hybrid nanoparticles with high tunability and anisotropy. Such combination is interesting, for instance, to be applied in combined magneto-photo-thermia,¹⁰ where the heat generated by the core-shell nanoparticles when exposed to alternating magnetic fields and external light radiation can be used for the treatment of different cancers through a thermal ablation mechanism. The combined thermal therapy enables the use of lower

nanoparticle concentrations as the heating efficiency is improved and overcomes the drawbacks of each one. These include the limited penetration depth of photothermia or the limited heating capabilities at low concentrations of magnetothermia, providing an enhanced versatility in its application and achieving synergistic effects on its treatment.¹¹⁻¹⁴ Despite its potential, Au NR shells with magnetic cores have only been implemented in γ -Fe₂O₃ (hematite) NRs.^{9,15,16} While they can be synthesized into a spindle shape, close to the NR shape, their functions are limited due to their antiferromagnetic nature. Instead, Fe₃O₄ (magnetite), a ferrimagnetic material, can offer high saturation magnetization, of around 92 Am²kg⁻¹,¹⁷ which can be translated into easier magnetic manipulation and magneto-thermal transduction while offering high biocompatibility. The versatility of hybrid Fe₃O₄-Au nanoparticles has been demonstrated by their many different applications, including the subattomole detection of cancer-associated biomarkers, targeted drug delivery, contaminants sensing, multimodal imaging, or hyperthermal therapy of cancer cells among others.^{18,19} Incorporating anisotropy to these multifunctional core-shell structures will add directionality and further tunability and versatility to those applications.

Unfortunately, in most cases, nanoparticles have a strong tendency to aggregate when dispersed in physiological media as a result of their high surface energy and protein and salt concentration.²⁰ The aggregation strongly influences the plasmonic resonance of photonic nanoparticles and thus the effectiveness in photothermal applications as well as the performance of magnetic nanomaterials highly decreasing their performance in magnetothermia.²¹ Additionally, the complete removal of nanoparticles from liquid media remains a challenge, resulting in undesired contamination effects. A possible approach to overcome this bottleneck is the effective immobilization of nanoparticles into a soft matrix. In this context, hydrogels emerge as a suitable host candidate due to their mechanically-soft character, compatibility with nanoparticles, biocompatibility, and ease of fabrication. Their use in combination with hyperthermia has been proposed in the treatment of cancers as well as regenerative medicine in

cancer-treated tissue as well as in drug delivery systems.²²⁻²⁴ Hydrogels can be defined as three-dimensional hydrophilic networks of cross-linked flexible chains retaining large amounts of water molecules.²⁵ Hydrogels behave as viscoelastic solids and are able to withstand large mechanical deformation with no fracture. Thanks to their versatility, both chemically- and physically-crosslinked hydrogels show a plethora of applications in a large variety of fields including catalysis,²⁶ biomedicine,²⁷ photonics,²⁵ or energy storage.²⁸

The implementation of nanocomposite hydrogels with permanent anisotropy will also impart additional features to classical isotropic hydrogels as the physico-chemical properties will vary depending on the orientation. For instance, anisotropic hydrogels are widely used in biomedicine with the aim of mimicking the structure of biological tissues.²⁹ Inspired by biological tissues, soft materials with anisotropic responsiveness in terms of mechanical and (de)swelling have been obtained, opening the path to soft actuators like smart robots.³⁰ In spite of these remarkable efforts mainly focused on mechanical properties, less attention has been paid to developing optically and magnetically anisotropic gels. In this sense, dispersing anisotropic materials within a hydrogel precursor and orienting those particles through external electric or magnetic fields results in an attractive approach given its versatility, simplicity, and effectiveness.^{31,32} As opposed to electrically-induced orientation which uses induced dipoles, magnetically-assisted orientation preserves the physicochemical features of the hosting matrix avoiding the often undesired decomposition when large electric fields are applied. Moreover, magnetic orientation can be uniformly applied throughout the whole sample and it is a non-contact approach.³² In comparison to hydrogels containing self-assembled nanoparticles forming filaments,³³ NRs, having intrinsic anisotropy, can be easily oriented inside uniform magnetic fields, without the necessity of high nanoparticle concentration and translation of nanoparticles in its interior.^{34,35}

This work demonstrates the fabrication of Au-coated rod-shaped magnetite nanoparticles ($\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4\text{-NR@Au}$) exhibiting optical and magnetic properties and their use to form anisotropic hydrogels with hyperthermia properties (**Scheme 1**). Fe_3O_4 NRs were synthesized with controlled geometrical features (length and width) changing the amount of hexadecylamine capping ligand. NRs were hybridized with Au nanoclusters to form core-satellite intermediate structures, which were further modified to grow a Au shell with a thickness between 5 and 25 nm. The morphological and optical properties of the nanoparticles were characterized as a function of the shell formation. The magnetically and optically active $\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4\text{-NR@Au}$ were then embedded and subsequently oriented within an agarose hydrogel to fabricate free-standing anisotropic materials with magneto- and photo-thermia properties with high potential in hyperthermia therapeutic applications. The use of hydrogel enables the understanding of the effect of orientation on the photo- and magneto-thermia. Thus, its characterization gives valuable information on the angular effect upon delivery in the tumor extracellular matrix and tumor cell interiors in the presence of a magnetic field before the hyperthermia therapy is applied. Besides, their use as hydrogel provides an interesting platform for relevant applications in the regeneration of removed cancer tissues thanks to its additional functionalities such as scaffold-like properties, or injectable and *in situ* forming gels. The nanoparticle synthetic route here reported can also be applied to other materials with magnetic and optical properties, expanding the horizons of anisotropic materials, for example, as filamentous hydrogels.

Scheme 1. Representation of the different steps followed to achieve the anisotropic gel and its use in magnetothermia. From top to down: Synthesis of the hybrid nanoparticles Fe₃O₄-NR@Au. Preparation of the nanoparticle-loaded anisotropic agarose hydrogel. Use of the loaded hydrogel in magneto- and photothermia with directional characteristics.

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

Materials

Oleic acid (90%, 364525-1L), hexadecylamine (HDA) for synthesis grade (8222030500), iron (0) pentacarbonyl (195731-50G), 1-octanol for synthesis grade (8209311000), formaldehyde (37 wt.% in H₂O, F1635-25ML), and polyvinylpyrrolidone powder (average M_w ~55,000 g·mol⁻¹), K₂CO₃ were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (MERCK). (3-aminopropyl) triethoxysilane, 98% (APTES, A10668), chloroform (>99.8%, 11352878), and hydrogen tetrachloroaurate(III) hydrate (HAuCl₄, 99.9%, 12325.06) were purchased from Alfa Aesar™ by Thermo Fisher Scientific. Agarose, D1 low EEO was purchased from Condolab. Absolut ethanol, EPR Ph.Eur., ≥ 99.5% V/V (ETHA-9TP-5K0) was purchased from Labbox.

Synthesis of Fe₃O₄ NRs

Magnetite NRs were synthesized by solvothermal method as reported by Si et al.³⁶ in a 50 mL Teflon-lined autoclave. First, 0.47 g of hexadecylamine and 5.33 mL of oleic acid were dissolved in 21.33 mL of 1-octanol at 45 °C under magnetic stirring until a homogenous liquid was obtained. Then, the solution was cooled to room temperature and 5.33 mL of Fe(CO)₅ were added and stirred for 2 min. Finally, the mixture was poured into the Teflon autoclave, sealed with its stainless steel shell, and heated at 200 °C for 6 h, without a heating ramp and after preheating the oven. After cooling to room temperature, the product was washed three times with ethanol and dispersed in 5 mL of chloroform (28.9 mg·mL⁻¹).

Fe₃O₄-NRs-satellite synthesis

Before the decoration of NRs with Au-satellites, NRs were functionalized with aminopropyltriethoxysilane (APTES), an aminosilane that substitutes oleic acid on NRs' surface, providing an amine rich coating. Typically, 100 µL of well dispersed NRs' solution were poured dropwise into a solution of 600 µL APTES : 5 mL ethanol and mixed by using a rotary tube mixer overnight. Then, the NRs were washed twice with ethanol and further dispersed in 3 mL ethanol.

Besides, spherical Au nanoparticles of 2-3 nm of diameter were synthesized. First, 0.9013 g of PVP were dissolved in 50 mL of ultrapure H₂O. Then, 429 µL of a solution of HAuCl₄ (50 mM) were added and the NPs were formed by reducing the Au⁺³ with 15 mL of NaBH₄ solution of 5.24 mM.

Finally, 3 mL of APTES functionalized NRs were added dropwise into 30 mL of Au-nanoparticles solution and mixed with a rotary tube mixer for 2 h. The core-satellite NRs were purified by centrifugation and the decoration process was repeated once more to improve the

satellite-coating of the NRs. Repeated cycles have been shown to improve the coating with satellites,³⁷ however based on the TEM images in our case after two cycles further improvement is not observed.

Fe₃O₄-NR@Au synthesis

A basic growth solution, k-gold was initially prepared: 5 mg of K₂CO₃ were dissolved in 19.7 mL of ultrapure H₂O for 15 minutes under magnetic stirring. Then, 150 μ L of HAuCl₄ solution 50 mM were added and mixed for 30 minutes where the solution gets colorless due to the reduction of Au⁺³ to Au⁺. 25 - 400 μ L of the solution of Fe₃O₄-NR-satellites (Fe₃O₄ = 1.26 mM; Au = 2.22 mM) were added under orbital stirring (see **Table 1**) to 1.6 mL of K-gold solution. After one minute, 2.6 μ L of formaldehyde was added to reduce the Au⁺ to metallic Au, where the surface of satellites acted as autocatalytic growing sites until a shell was formed by fusion of the growing satellites, completely covering the NRs. After 2 h, the reaction was complete and no change was further observed in the UV-Vis spectrum. The nanoparticles were then centrifuged and cleaned in two extra centrifugation cycles with ultrapure water, and finally dispersed with 5 mL of water.

Table 1. Conditions of added NR-satellites and Au growth solution of the prepared samples. The concentration values of satellites and magnetite are separately expressed. In addition, HAuCl₄/Fe₃O₄ molar ratio is indicated.

Sample	Fe₃O₄ (mM)	Au-satellites (mM)	HAuCl₄ (mM)/ Fe₃O₄ (mM)
1	3.41	6.07	0.08
2	1.97	3.51	0.16
3	1.07	1.91	0.32

4	0.56	1.00	0.64
5	0.29	0.51	1.27

Agarose hydrogel nanocomposites

To develop the hydrogels, firstly a dispersion of agarose in water at 2 wt.% was heated by using a microwave at 800 W for 30 seconds (80-90 °C) and it was allowed to cool down. Then the solution of Fe₃O₄-NR@Au dispersed at 45 °C was poured within the agarose solution and homogenized in an ultrasound bath. The composite hydrogel was finally poured into a mold (typically polystyrene cuvettes are employed) where the physical crosslinking takes place at room temperature between two magnets as shown in **Scheme 1**.

Characterization methods

Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) images were acquired in a JEOL JEM-1400 PLUS instrument operating at 100 kV, after nanoparticles were deposited on a carbon-coated TEM grid. High-resolution TEM (HR-TEM) was performed in Thermo Fisher Talos-F200 TEM working at 200 KV. The nanoparticle morphological features were analyzed with the Image J software package.

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) measurements were performed in the SPECS instrument (Berlin, Germany) equipped with an analyzer Phoibos150 1D-DLD and monochromatic radiation source Al K α (1486.7 eV). A first quick wide scan was carried out to determine the present elements (step energy 1 eV, dwell time 0.1 s, pass energy 80 eV) and then a detailed analysis was performed for the different elements (step energy 0.08 eV, dwell time 0.1 s, pass energy 30 eV) with an electron outgoing angle of 90°. The spectrometer was previously calibrated with Ag (Ag 3d_{5/2}, 368.26 eV). The spectra were fit with the software

CasaXPS 2.3.16, which models the Gauss-Lorentzian contributions after a background subtraction (Shirley). Concentrations were calculated correcting the values with the relative atomic sensitivity factors (Scofield).

UV-Vis spectroscopy: The absorbance of nanoparticle solutions was recorded using a Cary 60 (Agilent) over the 300–1100 nm range in a standard Macro cuvette using diluted aqueous solutions.

Elemental Analysis: It was measured in a quadrupole mass spectrometer with Inductively Coupled Plasma (ICP) source (Q-ICP-MS), model XSeries-II (Thermo). An internal standard was introduced by adding 100 μL of Yttrium at 500 ppb. The measured selected isotopes to perform the quantification were ^{57}Fe and ^{197}Au . Nanoparticle samples (typically 50 μL) were added to 100 μL of aqua regia (1:3 HNO_3 : HCl , trace analysis grade), and left for digestion for 1 hour. The sample was then diluted with milli-Q water to 10 mL (further diluted if necessary) and measured by ICP.

XRD: X-ray powder diffraction (XRD) patterns were collected by using a Philips X'pert PRO automatic diffractometer operating at 40 kV and 40 mA, in theta-theta configuration, secondary monochromator with Cu-K α radiation ($\lambda = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$) and a PIXcel solid-state detector (active length in 2θ 3.347°). 1° fixed soller and divergence slit giving a constant volume of sample illumination were used. X-ray phi-scans were collected by using a Bruker D8 Discover diffractometer equipped with a Cr Twist tube, V filter ($\lambda = 2.2911 \text{ \AA}$), PolyCapTM (1 μ single crystal cylinders) system for parallel beam generation (divergence of 0.25°), and a 1-D LynxEye detector (active length in 2θ 2.7°). The samples were mounted on an Eulerian Cradle with an automatic controlled X-Y-Z stage.

VSM: Magnetic hysteresis loops were measured at room temperature using a MicroSense EZ7 vibrating sample magnetometer (VSM) from -1.8 to 1.8 T.

AC Magnetometry: AC hysteresis loops were measured using a homemade AC magnetometer as previously described.³⁸ Briefly, it consists of an air-core inductor part of a resonant circuit fed by a power amplifier. The dynamic magnetization, $M(t)$, is obtained by a pick-up coil system composed of two coils wound in opposite directions. The device is capable of working in a wide frequency range (100kHz-1MHz) with large field intensities: up to 90 mT at low frequencies and up to 30 mT at high frequencies. A hydrogel solution containing 100 μ L of 2 % agarose and the NRs at 3 mg/mL was introduced in a plastic capsule and left to gel in the presence of a DC magnetic field. Then, the AC hysteresis loops were measured at 133 kHz frequency and field intensities up to 90 mT. The measurements were carried out in NR and Fe₃O₄-NR@Au of different sizes ($L=52 \pm 7$ nm, $L= 140 \pm 11$ nm and $L= 397 \pm 49$ nm) oriented parallel, perpendicular and random to the applied magnetic field. The specific absorption rate (SAR) was extracted by computing the area (A) enclosed by the loops, multiplied by the number of loops per second (frequency) and normalized by the sample concentration (mass per unit volume of the colloidal sample):

$$SAR \left(\frac{W}{g} \right) = \frac{f}{c} A = \frac{f}{c} \mu_0 \oint M dH \quad (1)$$

Photothermia: 1 mL of the Fe₃O₄-NR@Au solution (2 wt.% of agarose, NRs at a 0.5 mM of Au) was passed to a spectroscopic fluorescence cuvette of PS with a 1x1 cm² section, and placed between two magnets to orient them while the gelation took place. For the photothermia, the cuvette was mounted in a specific holder located behind a 1x1 cm mask, and irradiated with an LED light using a 10 W LED at 735 nm and an aspheric collimating lens. The current of the LED was controlled with a power source to have final irradiance of 0.2 W·cm⁻². Additionally, laser illumination was performed with a Lumics, LuOcean Mini4, working at 785nm and 0.3 W·cm⁻² and a silver reflector collimator (Thorlabs). The temperature was measured from the top using a thermal camera (Flir E4) and evaluated with the Flir tools+ software package. Light intensity was measured using a power sensor behind the cuvette (S425, Thorlabs).

The temperature variation was measured as a function of time (dT / dt) at the initial linear slope ($t \approx 1$ min) in order to evaluate power dissipation, *i.e.* the SAR ($W \cdot g^{-1}$) per mass of the active element Au. The SAR was then calculated using the following formula:

$$SAR = \frac{c_{gel} M_{gel}}{M_{Au}} \frac{dT}{dt} \quad (2)$$

where c_{gel} is the specific heat that was taken as the specific heat of water ($4.185 \text{ KJ} \cdot \text{Kg}^{-1} \cdot \text{K}^{-1}$), M_{gel} is the sample mass that is approximately the water mass, and M_{Au} is the mass of nanorods Au.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Magnetite nanorods

Iron oxide NRs were initially synthesized by a solvothermal method in octanol using iron pentacarbonyl as an iron source, and oleic acid and HDA as capping ligands. **Figures 1a-e** show representative TEM images of synthesized NRs at different sizes. In general, highly monodisperse single-crystal NRs with well-defined shapes were obtained. **Figure 1f** shows a HR-TEM image of a single NR. The lattice fringes corresponding to the (220) planes of magnetite can be observed, with a spacing of nearly 0.29 nm, as expected for a NR growing in the [110] direction.^{39,40} The different sizes were achieved by varying the amount of HDA capping ligand (**Figure 1g**). Both, length and width of the NRs decrease when increasing the amount of HDA with a similar linear trend in the HDA range from 0.18 to 0.53 g. The shortest NRs were obtained at 0.53 g of HDA, exhibiting a length of 52 ± 7 nm and a width of 6.2 ± 0.9 nm (aspect ratio, A.R. = 8.4 ± 1.7). Within this region, the longest rods were obtained at 0.18 g of HDA, presenting a length of 275 ± 23 nm, and a width of 39.4 ± 3.9 nm (A.R. = 7.0 ± 0.9). Nevertheless, a change in the growth kinetic was observed when 0.70 g of HDA were added,

obtaining the largest NRs (length = 397 ± 49 nm, width = 45.2 ± 6.1 nm) probably due to the complex interplay between nucleation and growth.

The formation of iron oxide NRs can be explained as competing effects between the decomposition of iron pentacarbonyl and the hydrolysis of iron oleate. Firstly, HDA and oleic acid condense, forming water and iron oleate. The oleic acid also acts as a capping ligand, which attached to nucleation points of magnetite avoids the growth of the crystals on determined planes and results in rod-shaped nanoparticles expanding into the [110] direction.^{40,41} Also, oleic acid avoids the oxidation of Fe^{+2} to Fe^{+3} and circumvents nanoparticle aggregation. To verify the crystalline structure of NRs, XRD experiments were conducted. As shown in **Figure S1a**, the characteristic crystalline structure of an inverse spinel is achieved. No peaks corresponding to any other phases were observed, indicating the high purity of the material. Since the XRD patterns of magnetite (Fe_3O_4) and maghemite ($\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$) are very similar,⁴² it is necessary to consider additional characterization so the oxidation state of iron can be distinguished (Fe^{2+} and Fe^{3+} for magnetite and solely Fe^{2+} for maghemite). The XPS results in **Figures S1b** and **S1c** confirm the magnetite composition, with binding energies of $2p_{3/2}$ and $2p_{1/2}$ and at 709.7 eV and 724.1 eV, respectively, and absence of satellite peak.⁴³

Figure 1. TEM images of the synthesized NRs at different amounts of the capping ligand HDA: (a) 0.53 g, (b) 0.47 g, (c) 0.35 g (d) 0.18 g (e) 0.70 g. Error bars correspond to the standard deviation of an average of 50 measured nanoparticles. (f) HRTEM of a NR from Figure 1(b). (g) Average sizes of the NRs in a-e (black squares: length, red circles: width, and blue triangles: aspect ratio (A.R.)) representing their evolution with the HDA and maintaining the rest of the parameters constant.

Au-coated Fe₃O₄ nanorods (NR@Au)

We then proceed to a Fe₃O₄ hybridization with Au nanoshell to impart, together with the magnetic, also optical properties to the nanoparticles. To that end, Fe₃O₄ NRs were coated with a Au shell through a multi-step process consisting of: i) silanization of the surface of magnetite NRs with aminopropyltriethoxysilane (APTES) and transfer to water; ii) anchoring small Au nanoclusters, < 3 nm, (Au-seeds) on the surface of NRs to form a NR core-satellite (Fe₃O₄-NR-satellite) structure; iii) grow the Au-seeds until a complete shell is obtained. This coating strategy has been previously used to coat different types of nanoparticles such as silica,^{37,44,45} or iron oxide,^{9,15} and avoids the formation of patches generated by the slightly different lattice parameter between metallic Au and the double lattice fringe of iron oxide preventing a good epitaxial growth along the whole NR.^{46,47} Hereafter, results will focus on the medium-sized NRs with 140 ± 11 nm (length) and 14.8 ± 1.2 nm (width). This NR size was selected as a good compromise to exhibit a suitable magnetothermal effect, a relatively small size to avoid sedimentation, and for being big enough for a good formation of a thick Au shell layer around while maintaining a rod shape. This synthesis uses formaldehyde, a well-known toxic compound, that ideally would need to be replaced in the pursuit of a greener and less toxic chemistry. However, replacing it with other greener reducing agents such as ascorbic acid or citrate gives rise to the formation of patches at the surface and/or secondary nucleation that form new gold nanoparticles. This is probably due to the highly autocatalytic reduction of K-gold by formaldehyde in which the gold is reduced mainly at the nanorods-satellite surface. Despite its use, formaldehyde is applied in very low concentrations, partially oxidized during the reaction, and removed in the successive cleaning steps giving rise to ppb and sub ppb remaining concentrations, below its cytotoxic threshold,⁴⁸ and making the nanoparticles safe for biomedical applications.

During the first step, silane groups are bound selectively to magnetite and a 2D polymerization of the silanes is produced at its surface. As a result, the nanoparticles exhibit

exposed amine groups that make them dispersible in water and a positive Zeta-potential of 14.5 ± 1.3 mV in ultrapure water. This leaves the NR surfaces available for Au-seeds linkage. In the next step, negatively charged Au-seeds and positively charged silanized NRs are mixed in an aqueous solution to form a new intermediate structure of NRs with Au-seeds attached to the surface amine functional groups, resulting in the so-called NR-satellites. Negative Zeta-potential values of -14.3 ± 1.7 mV indicated the successful attachment of Au-seeds. Finally, a complete shell was obtained upon the reduction of the extra amount of Au, from a Au growth solution (K-gold) of HAuCl_4 and K_2CO_3 on the NR-satellites and by using formaldehyde as a reducing agent. Au-satellites act as growing sites so metallic Au is formed on their surface finally merging and forming a complete shell. **Figure 2a** schematically shows the TEM images of NRs at different degrees of Au-coating, starting with Fe_3O_4 -NR-satellites ($\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4 = 1.26$ mM; $\text{Au} = 2.22$ mM) until a thick shell of Au is obtained (corresponding TEM images are shown in **Figure S2**). The differences in the shell formation were obtained by adjusting the ratio between Fe_3O_4 -NR-satellites and HAuCl_4 , (see **Table 1** in the experimental section).

UV-vis was conducted to get further insights into the state of the shell. As shown in Figure 2b, the Fe_3O_4 -NR-satellite solution presents a dark-brown color (sample 0; left vial in the photograph) without a peak in the visible spectrum. On the contrary, sample 1, having a small ratio of Au growth solution/NR-satellites (HAuCl_4 (mM)/ Fe_3O_4 (mM) = 0.08), turns into a lilac (or pale violet) color with a maximum absorbance peak at 543 nm. This effect is ascribed to the growth of the Au satellites onto Fe_3O_4 surfaces. In samples 2 and 3, satellites are big enough to touch and start merging each other, although a complete shell is not formed. They present bluish color, where the maximum absorbance shifts to higher wavelengths of 556 and 568 nm, respectively, and a high increase of the absorbance at the near Infrared (NIR) (Au layer in sample 3 is 12.7 ± 4.6 nm thick) is observed. A complete lumpy shell (Fe_3O_4 -NR@Au) of 16.6 ± 3.6 nm thick was obtained for sample 4, where two maximum absorbance peaks appear at

537 and 613 nm and a large tail that extends up to the NIR region are observed. This is somehow similar to previously reported Au coated hematite spindles,⁹ however in this case a very broad peak from the reds to the near IR region was obtained. This broad peak could be interpreted as a mixture between the expected peak of the nanoshell-rod hybridization mode and the modes of the bumpy rough surface of the NR, somehow similar to a quasy-nanostar morphology. Finally, a 25.0 ± 4.5 nm thick Au shell can be observed for sample 5, which presents only one narrower peak at 538 nm with additional absorption in the infrared region. Based on this, samples with the thinnest but complete shells are optimal for a photothermal therapy using NIR light. The complete shell is required as a protective layer for the magnetite to help maintain its properties during therapeutic use. On the other hand, thicker shells produce undesired shifts of the plasmonic bands to lower wavelengths. Therefore sample 4 shows the most desirable characteristics for photothermia, and although the maximum absorbance is still around 613 nm, the broad band at the NIR covers the whole first transparency window of biological tissue with a relatively high extinction coefficient, which is, as shown below, more than enough to drive an effective photothermal effect. Note here that this absorption is mainly due to the absorption of the gold part as iron oxide shows a limited extinction coefficient at these wavelengths and would require several orders of magnitude higher concentration to achieve photothermia (**Figure S3** shows the UV-Vis of nanorods before and after gold coating).^{49,50}

Figure 2. a) TEM image of the rods at different growth conditions. Sample 0 corresponds to Fe_3O_4 -NR-satellites structure, and the subsequent samples (1-5) were prepared increasing the amount of the ratio [K-gold]/[NR-satellite seeds], generating different degrees of core-satellites until a complete core-shell is obtained. b) UV-Vis spectra of the solution of the different nanoparticles and their pictures showing the differences in the optical properties (a).

Agarose/NR and agarose/ Fe_3O_4 -NR@Au composite hydrogels

Fe_3O_4 -NR@Au were then incorporated into a polymeric matrix to obtain a free-standing material with magnetic and optical properties. Anisotropic hydrogels were prepared by dispersing NRs into aqueous agarose solutions (previously dissolved by microwave) at 45 °C in an ultrasonic bath and then placing the mixture between the gap of two magnets at 0.32 T (see **Scheme 1**). In these conditions, the NRs orientate according to the applied magnetic fields

due to magnetic dipolar interactions and the relatively low viscosity of the media. Once the temperature decreases below the gel point, the gelation process arrests the structure. In other words, the gelation traps the nanoparticles into the oriented condition. The mechanical properties of the agarose hydrogels at different NPs concentrations were measured to determine their capacity to withstand externally applied compressive forces. **Figure S4a** shows representative uniaxial compressive stress–strain curves of neat agarose hydrogels at concentrations ranging from 0.5 to 3 wt.%. The curves are characterized by an elastic behavior at strains up to 20 % where the compressive stress increases linearly with strain, followed by a plastic deformation region (20 to 60 % strain) and a final stiffening region at strains exceeding 60 %.⁵¹ Generally, all the gels show good deformability as they are able to accommodate large strain without breaking. Compressive modulus values of 7.9-180.9 kPa were achieved for the 0.5-3 wt.% compositions. Those values are similar to hydrogels formed by other biopolymers, including cellulose nanocrystal hydrogels (7 kPa),⁵² or the 25-85 kPa for cellulose nanofibers.⁵³ The increased modulus with agarose concentration results from the formation of extensive physical crosslinks between agarose chains through weak interactions, yielding a mechanically robust three-dimensional structure.⁵⁴ In addition, agarose hydrogels comprising a 0.1 wt.% of Fe₃O₄-NR@Au were tested to study the effect of the Fe₃O₄-NR@Au at different orientations inside the hydrogel matrix. The parameters of hydrogel, at this concentration, remain very similar and comparable to the neat agarose hydrogel. When using agarose at 1 wt.%, however, a displacement of the NRs inside the hydrogel during the magnetic characterization curves was observed. This displacement/rotation was not visualized magnetically at concentrations of 2 wt.% and above, where the nanorods were arrested inside of the hydrogel and no changes were observed in the magnetic behavior after exposing them to magnetic fields. Based on mechanical and magnetic results, we decided to prepare the composite hydrogels at 2 wt.% of agarose due to its fabrication simplicity by microwave heating, its suitable mechanical strength, easiness to

manipulate, and the adequate entrapment of NRs (**Figure S4b**). Both magnetite NRs and Fe₃O₄-NR@Au were prepared in this way and characterized magnetically and optically.

Besides, the strong and fast gelling character upon cooling the dispersion to temperatures below the gelling point offers an interesting platform to incorporate synthesized nanoparticles.⁵⁵ More interestingly, like many other polysaccharides, agarose dispersions show a characteristic shear-thinning behavior.⁵⁶ This property encourages us to also fabricate magnetically active injectable hydrogels, where water-based agarose/NR hybrids are injected by application of shear stresses and quickly self-heal after the removal of shear forces.⁵⁷ As shown in **Figure S5**, after a warm water-based agarose/Fe₃O₄-NRs@Au dispersion was injected into an aqueous solution with a retracting movement, they form smooth and continuous hydrogel filaments with a dark color as a result of the optically and magnetically active core-shell nanoparticles. The combination of such magnetic-optic properties and their injectable character makes these materials suitable for localized cancer therapies, outperforming traditional cancer treatments.⁵⁸ The ability to obtain filaments is also interesting for biomedical applications where large surface areas are preferred,⁵⁹ as well as the generation of novel avenues for the development of (magnetically) externally-triggered drug delivery applications, allowing a new family of minimally invasive on-demand drug delivery systems.⁶⁰

Magnetic properties of hydrogels

With the aim to determine the magnetic properties of the NRs, a powder of NRs, prepared by evaporating the solvent overnight in vacuum conditions, was analyzed through VSM. A saturation magnetization (M_S) of 83.1 Am²kg⁻¹, a remanence (M_R) of 16.8 Am²kg⁻¹ and a coercive field (H_C) of 8.0 mT were obtained (see supplementary **Figure S6**). The obtained M_S showed low values in comparison with the bulk value of 92 Am²kg⁻¹.⁶¹ This could be ascribed to a combination of the coating of a non-magnetic oleic acid/HDA monolayer, coated surface's

electrostatic interactions, and the formation of aggregates that quench the saturation magnetization.^{62,63}

When 0.065 mg of the NRs were incorporated into the hydrogel under a magnetic field, the NRs got oriented inside it. In fact, as observed in optical microscopy pictures of the prepared hydrogels in **Figure 3a**, the field-directed assembly process induced the formation of linear NR assemblies, with microscopic NR lines parallel to the observed external magnetic field, and dark points in the perpendicular direction. This orientation is obtained thanks to the elongated shape of the NRs which confers a marked shape anisotropy, where the long axis is considered as the easy magnetization axis and a dipole-dipole interaction between the NRs takes place. On the contrary, for samples of non-oriented NRs, a homogenous color of the sample, without the presence of any darker spot, was observed.

M-H hysteresis loops of the NR-loaded hydrogels were measured in a random, parallel, and perpendicular direction and represented in **Figure 3b**. The marked differences in the hysteresis loops demonstrate the anisotropy with respect to the composite hydrogel in the random orientation of loaded NRs. Both the random and parallel oriented samples exhibit a similar coercive field of 10.2 and 10.6 mT, respectively, which is slightly higher in comparison with the powder sample. Interestingly, the loop measured in the parallel direction reaches faster saturation at a field (H_S , indicated with dashed lines) of 155 mT as compared to the random orientation loop ($H_S = 242$ mT). In addition, larger M_R ($13.7 \text{ Am}^2 \cdot \text{kg}^{-1}$) was measured for parallel orientation than for randomly distributed NRs ($M_R = 8.05 \times 10^{-4} \text{ Am}^2 \cdot \text{kg}^{-1}$). As expected, the opposite effect was observed for perpendicularly oriented NRs, where lower values of $H_C = 76$ mT and $M_R = 5.77 \times 10^{-4} \text{ Am}^2 \cdot \text{kg}^{-1}$ and slower curve with $H_S = 320$ mT were measured. These results demonstrate that synthesized magnetite NRs presented enough magnetic susceptibility to be aligned within the hydrogel. The anisotropy of the gel containing oriented NRs was further demonstrated using X-ray Azimuthal angle plots. As seen in **Figure S7** for the

in plane [311] peak, a high angular variation is observed. The separation of 180 degrees between both maximum intensities is indicative of the single-crystal NRs orientation inside of the gel. Finally, **Figure 3c** shows the magnetic behavior of Fe₃O₄-NR@Au (0.6 mg) within a hydrogel under a magnetic field. Similar differences between parallel, perpendicular and random to those of the pure NRs are achieved, indicating that even with the additional weight and volume of the non-magnetic material, the NRs were still able to orientate and assemble prior to the gelation of agarose. Despite this, higher slightly higher values of remanence and coercitivity are observed for the three configurations, which, as discussed below, can improve the magnetothermal effect.

Figure 3. a) Optical microscopy pictures of the gel at agarose 2 wt.% and loaded with 0.065 mg of NR, taken parallel to the magnetic field applied (left) and in a perpendicular direction (right) where alignment of elongated structures can be observed. b) Corresponding magnetic hysteresis loops of gels, measured in VSM, for non-oriented NRs, perpendicular, and parallel-oriented NRs. Dashed lines indicate the magnetic field applied when the M_s is reached (H_s) for each orientation. The inset shows a magnified view of the hysteresis loops. c) Magnetic hysteresis loops of the gels at 2 wt.%, measured in VSM, for perpendicular, and parallel-oriented, comprising 0.6 mg of $\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4\text{-NR@Au}$. The inset shows a magnified view of the hysteresis loops.

Magnetic hyperthermia

Magnetic hyperthermia offers a non-toxic, local and selective solution for the treatment of tumors by producing local heating through the application of external magnetic fields.⁶⁴ Accordingly, the magnetothermal capabilities of the hydrogel containing NRs of three different sizes, with lengths of 52, 140, and 397 nm, were tested with different configurations: with the alignment parallel to the magnetic field, perpendicular to the magnetic field, and without a preferential orientation, i.e. random. In this case, relatively large amounts of NRs ($3\text{mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$) were needed due to the sensibility of the equipment. To characterize the magnetothermal effect of the NR, their AC hysteresis loops were measured and the SAR was directly obtained from the area of the loops using an AC magnetometer previously described.³⁸ These measurements allow precise quantification of the power generated by integrating the area of the hysteresis loops. At first view, a high difference is appreciated in AC hysteresis loops shape when comparing the three different configurations (see **Figure 4a-c** for 140 ± 11 nm NRs). The perpendicular configuration shows narrow and elongated hysteresis loops while the parallel configuration shows a more square shape with a higher area. The case of the random configuration remains in between both configurations. Similar shapes have been reported for instance in magnetotactic bacteria dispersed in agar, somehow similar to a rod shapes, under random and parallel orientation.⁶⁵ The SAR was calculated as a function of the applied magnetic field for the three NR lengths and the three configurations (**Figure 4d-f**). The results show a sigmoidal shape, and for the case of parallel oriented configuration, the increase in SAR begins at much lower magnetic fields than for the perpendicular configuration. In fact, the sigmoidal middle point (magnetic field at half maximum of the sigmoid) is 20-30 mT lower for the perpendicular than for the parallel case (20, 26 and 30 mT for the 52, 140, and 357 nm NRs respectively). For the case of randomly oriented NRs it shows intermediate values. Additionally,

the maximum SAR value, obtained at high magnetic fields, was also dependent on the orientation, achieving the highest values for the case of parallel configuration and the lowest ones for the perpendicular case. Therefore, the use of oriented NRs seems an efficient strategy for achieving an enhanced SAR that allows the use of lower quantities of nanoparticles or alternatively the decrease of magnetic field and frequencies, to achieve similar effects to other non-anisotropic iron oxides nanoparticles. Additionally, the high difference between parallel and perpendicular configurations opens the door to a fine-tuning of the magnetothermal effect by varying the angle of application of magnetic fields.

The change of NR length did not seem to produce a big variation in the measured SAR value, the small differences could be on the other hand due to small differences in the NRs concentration or small portions of aggregation. To see the influence of the Au shell on the magnetothermal effect, the 140 nm length NRs were coated with Au. This NR size (140 ± 11 nm length) was chosen as a compromise to have a NR big enough to have a relatively homogenous coating, while not too big to have nanoparticle sedimentation. The SAR for the three configurations of Fe_3O_4 -NRs@Au ($3\text{mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ of Fe_3O_4 , $150\text{mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ of Fe_3O_4 -NRs@Au) can be observed in **Figure 4g**. This graph shows very similar results to the non-coated nanoparticles, with the parallel configuration showing a higher maximum SAR at high fields but interestingly, unlike the case of non-coated NRs, it shows that the beginning of SAR increases at similar magnetic fields for the three different configurations. The values are higher than the non-coated nanoparticles, attributed to a dipolar decoupling due to the Au shell spacer between the nanoparticles, similar to what has been seen to other coated magnetic nanoparticles.⁶⁶ This dipolar decoupling produces a more squared hysteresis loop with higher remanence and coercivity which is translated into a higher heat generated per magnetic cycle.

Plasmonic hyperthermia

The same Fe₃O₄-NRs@Au were used to form a gel for photothermal transduction. In this case, due to the much higher efficiency of plasmonic photothermia, a much lower concentration was used (0.1 mg·mL⁻¹ instead of 3 mg·mL⁻¹ for magnetothermia). The gel was formed inside a fluorescence cuvette and oriented in one of the directions (parallel to the cuvette base). The gel was irradiated with NIR (735 nm) light from one side of the cuvette either parallel or perpendicular to the NRs@Au inside the cuvette using an LED light and being the temperature monitored from above with a thermal camera. LED light was chosen as a simple, cheap, and highly available illumination source, while 735 nm is located at the middle of the first transparency window where minimum absorption by living tissue takes place. The gel showed high photothermal efficiency, with an increment of the temperature of more than 20 °C for a low light power of 0.2 W (**Figure 4h**), which is harmless for tissues such skin or other internal tissues,^{67,68} and a low nanoparticle concentration. When comparing the two configurations, however, very similar results were obtained, only marginally superior for the case of parallel configuration. This unexpected result is probably due to the complexity of the plasmonic modes of the nanoparticles that produce a very broad plasmonic band that comprises the nanoshell modes plus the additional modes of the bumpy surface of the nanoparticles, which makes it difficult to excite uniquely the longitudinal and transversal hybridized modes. The photothermal SAR was calculated for this sample in terms of the Au mass as the photothermal active element. Values of 2.18 and 2.36 KW g⁻¹ for parallel and perpendicular configuration respectively were obtained for the given setup conditions (0.2 W·cm⁻², 735 nm). These values are one order of magnitude higher than the ones obtained in magnetothermia and in the same order of magnitude that other reported plasmonic structures,^{69,70} in particular after considering the low power used here (corresponding to a SAR of 11.8 KW g⁻¹ per watt of irradiating light). In addition, although the NIR absorbance is slightly lower than the one taking place at the maximum around 613 nm (**Figure 2**) it has shown to be highly efficient to trigger the photothermal effect and its broad profile makes it practical for the use of any

wavelength within the first transparency window. In fact, using laser light at a higher wavelength, 785 nm, generates similar results with a SAR of 10.3 KW g⁻¹ per watt of irradiation light (Figure S8).

Figure 4. AC magnetometry measurements of agarose hydrogel at 2 wt.% loaded with 3 mg·mL⁻¹ of magnetite NRs of a length of 140 nm in (a) parallel, (b) random, and (c) perpendicular orientations measured at 133 kHz. SAR dependent of the applied magnetic field of different sized NRs: (d) $L = 52 \pm 7$ nm, (e) $L = 140 \pm 11$ nm and (f) $L = 397 \pm 49$ nm. Magnetothermia (g) and photothermia (h) of $\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4\text{-NR@Au}$ were also measured.

CONCLUSIONS

The successful synthesis of novel Fe₃O₄@Au NRs and their tunability in both nanoparticle dimension and shell thickness has been demonstrated by varying the HDA capping ligand and the ratio of seeds to Au, respectively. Developed core-shell materials show magnetic and photonic properties and tailored sizes for magneto- and photo-thermal anisotropic transductions. The NRs were successfully aligned within a hydrogel upon cooling in the presence of a magnetic field. The gel showed a clear anisotropy, as demonstrated by magnetical and XRD experiments. This gel offers the possibility to produce simultaneous magneto- and photothermia which can be used as dual therapy either in regenerative medicine or in cancer ablation, in which the synergistic effect and the possibility to induce anisotropic response can help to lower the therapeutic doses in terms of nanoparticles, light irradiation, or magnetic field applied. Moreover, obtained magnetic filament hydrogels upon injection offer suitable characteristics to be applied in localized therapies. Its use also opens the door to further technological applications where directionality and dual magnetic and optical properties are required, such as sensors or actuators, among others.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information

The Supporting Information is available free of charge on the ACS Publications website at <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/XXX>.

X-Ray diffraction, X-Ray photoelectron spectroscopy, transmission electron microscopy additional images, representative stress–strain compression curves, optical photographs, magnetic hysteresis loops, and UV-Vis spectra of the synthesized nanorods. Hydrogel temperature increase, optical photographs, and scanning electron microscopy images are provided.

AUTHOR INFORMATION

Corresponding Author

E-mail address: erlantz.liizundia@ehu.eus; javier.reguera@bcmaterials.net

ORCID[®]

Mikel Rincón-Iglesias: [0000-0001-7401-7495](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7401-7495)

Senentxu Lanceros-Méndez: [0000-0001-6791-7620](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6791-7620)

Erlantz Lizundia: [0000-0003-4013-2721](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4013-2721)

Javier Reguera: [0000-0003-4977-7948](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4977-7948)

Author Contributions

The manuscript was written through contributions of all authors. All authors have given approval to the final version of the manuscript.

Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

Acknowledgements

This work has been funded by the Spanish State Research Agency (AEI) through the project PID2019-106099RB-C43/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and the Basque Government Industry and Education Departments under the ELKARTEK program (PIBA-2018-06) and IT-1005-16 Grants, respectively. M.R.I. thanks the Department of Education of the Basque Government as grantee of the program “Programa Predoctoral de Formación de Personal Investigador”. I.R. thanks the support of the “Programa de Perfeccionamiento de Personal Investigador Doctor, Gobierno Vasco” under Grant POS-2020-1-0028 and Grant IT-1005-16. The authors thank the technical and human support provided by SGIker (UPV/EHU/ ERDF, EU).

References

- (1) Mohapatra, S.; Nguyen, T. A.; Nguyen-Tri, P. *Noble Metal-Metal Oxide Hybrid Nanoparticles: Fundamentals and Applications* Elsevier **2018**, 1–674.
- (2) Benelmekki, M. *Designing Hybrid Nanoparticles* Morgan & Claypool Publishers **2015**, 1–68.
- (3) Reguera, J.; Hyewon, K.; Setlacci, F. Advances in Janus Nanoparticles. *Chim. Int. J. Chem.* **2013**, *67* (11), 811–818.
- (4) Rittikulsittichai, S.; Kolhatkar, A. G.; Sarangi, S.; Vorontsova, M. A.; Vekilov, P. G.; Brazdeikis, A.; Randall Lee, T. Multi-Responsive Hybrid Particles: Thermo-, pH-, Photo-, and Magneto-Responsive Magnetic Hydrogel Cores with Gold Nanorod Optical Triggers. *Nanoscale* **2016**, *8* (23), 11851–11861.
- (5) Ghosh Chaudhuri, R.; Paria, S. Core/Shell Nanoparticles: Classes, Properties, Synthesis Mechanisms, Characterization, and Applications. *Chem. Rev.* **2012**, *112* (4), 2373–2433.
- (6) Burrows, N. D.; Vartanian, A. M.; Abadeer, N. S.; Grzincic, E. M.; Jacob, L. M.; Lin, W.; Li, J.; Dennison, J. M.; Hinman, J. G.; Murphy, C. J. Anisotropic Nanoparticles and Anisotropic Surface Chemistry. *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* **2016**, *7* (4), 632–641.
- (7) Link, S.; Mohamed, M. B.; El-Sayed, M. A. Simulation of the Optical Absorption Spectra of Gold Nanorods as a Function of Their Aspect Ratio and the Effect of the Medium Dielectric Constant. *J. Phys. Chem. B* **1999**, *103* (16), 3073–3077.
- (8) Prodan, E.; Radloff, C.; Halas, N. J.; Nordlander, P. A Hybridization Model for the Plasmon Response of Complex Nanostructures. *Science* **2003**, *302* (5644), 419–422.
- (9) Wang, H.; Brandl, D. W.; Le, F.; Nordlander, P.; Halas, N. J. Nanorice: A Hybrid Plasmonic Nanostructure. *Nano Lett.* **2006**, *6* (4), 827–832.
- (10) Cazares-Cortes, E.; Cabana, S.; Boitard, C.; Nehlig, E.; Griffete, N.; Fresnais, J.; Wilhelm, C.; Abou-Hassan, A.; Ménager, C. Recent Insights in Magnetic Hyperthermia: From the “Hot-Spot” Effect for Local Delivery to Combined Magneto-Photo-Thermia Using Magneto-Plasmonic Hybrids. *Adv. Drug Deliv. Rev.* **2019**, *138*, 233–246.
- (11) Espinosa, A.; Kolosnjaj-Tabi, J.; Abou-Hassan, A.; Plan Sangnier, A.; Curcio, A.; Silva, A. K. A.; Di Corato, R.; Neveu, S.; Pellegrino, T.; Liz-Marzán, L. M.; Wilhelm, C. Magnetic (Hyper)Thermia or Photothermia? Progressive Comparison of Iron Oxide and Gold Nanoparticles Heating in Water, in Cells, and In Vivo. *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2018**, *28* (37), 1803660.
- (12) Espinosa, A.; Reguera, J.; Curcio, A.; Muñoz-Noval, Á.; Kuttner, C.; Walle, A. Van De; Liz-marzán, L. M.; Wilhelm, C. Janus Magnetic-Plasmonic Nanoparticles for Magnetically Guided and Thermally Activated Cancer Therapy. *Small* **2020**, *16* (11), 1904960.
- (13) Alphanbéry, E. Bio-Synthesized Iron Oxide Nanoparticles for Cancer Treatment. *Int. J. Pharm.* **2020**, *586*, 119472.
- (14) Alphanbéry, E. Applications of Magnetotactic Bacteria and Magnetosome for Cancer Treatment: A Review Emphasizing on Practical and Mechanistic Aspects. *Drug Discov. Today* **2020**, *25* (8), 1444–1452.
- (15) Spuch-Calvar, M.; Pérez-Juste, J.; Liz-Marzán, L. M. Hematite Spindles with Optical Functionalities: Growth of Gold Nanoshells and Assembly of Gold Nanorods. *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* **2007**, *310* (1), 297–301.
- (16) Ma, Z.; Han, H.; Tu, S.; Xue, J. Fabrication of Shape-Controlled Hematite Particles and Growth of Gold

- Nanoshells. *Colloids Surfaces A Physicochem. Eng. Asp.* **2009**, *334* (1–3), 142–146.
- (17) Sun, S.; Zeng, H.; Robinson, D. B.; Raoux, S.; Rice, P. M.; Wang, S. X.; Li, G. Monodisperse MFe_2O_4 (M = Fe, Co, Mn) Nanoparticles. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2004**, *126* (1), 273–279.
- (18) Larson, T. A.; Bankson, J.; Aaron, J.; Sokolov, K. Hybrid Plasmonic Magnetic Nanoparticles as Molecular Specific Agents for MRI/Optical Imaging and Photothermal Therapy of Cancer Cells. *Nanotechnology* **2007**, *18* (32), 325101.
- (19) Reguera, J.; de Aberasturi, D.; Henriksen-Lacey, M.; Langer, J.; Espinosa, A.; Szczupak, B.; Wilhelm, C.; Liz-Marzán, L. M. Janus Plasmonic-Magnetic Gold-Iron Oxide Nanoparticles as Contrast Agents for Multimodal Imaging. *Nanoscale* **2017**, *9* (27), 9467–9480.
- (20) Grzelczak, M.; Vermant, J.; Furst, E. M.; Liz-Marzán, L. M. Directed Self-Assembly of Nanoparticles. *ACS Nano* **2010**, *4* (7), 3591–3605.
- (21) Castellanos-Rubio, I.; Rodrigo, I.; Olazagoitia-Garmendia, A.; Arriortua, O.; Gil de Muro, I.; Garitaonandia, J. S.; Bilbao, J. R.; Fdez-Gubieda, M. L.; Plazaola, F.; Orue, I.; Castellanos-Rubio, A.; Insausti, M. Highly Reproducible Hyperthermia Response in Water, Agar and Cellular Environment by Discretely PEGylated Magnetite Nanoparticles. *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2020**, *12*, 27917–27929.
- (22) Häring, M.; Schiller, J.; Mayr, J.; Grijalvo, S.; Eritja, R.; Díaz, D. D. Magnetic Gel Composites for Hyperthermia Cancer Therapy. *Gels* **2015**, *1* (2), 135–161.
- (23) Banobre-Lopez, M.; Pineiro-Redondo, Y.; Sandri, M.; Tampieri, A.; De Santis, R.; Dediu, V. A.; Rivas, J. Hyperthermia Induced in Magnetic Scaffolds for Bone Tissue Engineering. *IEEE Trans. Magn.* **2014**, *50* (11), 5400507.
- (24) Salmani, M. M.; Hashemian, M.; Hamed, & Yekta, J.; Mazyar, & Nejad, G.; Saber-Samandari, S.; Khandan, A. Synergic Effects of Magnetic Nanoparticles on Hyperthermia-Based Therapy and Controlled Drug Delivery for Bone Substitute Application. *J. Supercond. Nov. Magn.* **2020**, *33*, 2809–2820.
- (25) Umar, M.; Min, K.; Kim, S. Advances in Hydrogel Photonics and Their Applications. *APL Photonics* **2019**, *4* (12), 120901.
- (26) Seto, H.; Matsumoto, H.; Miura, Y. Preparation of Palladium-Loaded Polymer Hydrogel Catalysts with High Durability and Recyclability. *Polym. J.* **2020**, *52* (7), 671–679.
- (27) De France, K. J.; Hoare, T.; Cranston, E. D. Review of Hydrogels and Aerogels Containing Nanocellulose. *Chem. Mater.* **2017**, *29* (11), 4609–4631.
- (28) Lizundia, E.; Kundu, D. Advances in Natural Biopolymer-Based Electrolytes and Separators for Battery Applications. *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2021**, *31* (3), 2005646.
- (29) Gila-Vilchez, C.; Mañas-Torres, M. C.; Contreras-Montoya, R.; Alaminos, M.; Duran, J. D. G.; de Cienfuegos, L. Á.; Lopez-Lopez, M. T. Anisotropic Magnetic Hydrogels: Design, Structure and Mechanical Properties. *Philos. Trans. R. Soc. A* **2019**, *377* (2143), 20180217.
- (30) Qin, H.; Zhang, T.; Li, N.; Cong, H.-P.; Yu, S.-H. Anisotropic and Self-Healing Hydrogels with Multi-Responsive Actuating Capability. *Nat. Commun.* **2019**, *10* (1), 2202.
- (31) Sano, K.; Ishida, Y.; Aida, T. Synthesis of Anisotropic Hydrogels and Their Applications. *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2018**, *57* (10), 2532–2543.

- (32) Yook, S.; Shams Es-haghi, S.; Yildirim, A.; Mutlu, Z.; Cakmak, M. Anisotropic Hydrogels Formed by Magnetically-Oriented Nanoclay Suspensions for Wound Dressings. *Soft Matter* **2019**, *15* (47), 9733–9741.
- (33) Hu, K.; Sun, J.; Guo, Z.; Wang, P.; Chen, Q.; Ma, M.; Gu, N. A Novel Magnetic Hydrogel with Aligned Magnetic Colloidal Assemblies Showing Controllable Enhancement of Magnetothermal Effect in the Presence of Alternating Magnetic Field. *Adv. Mater.* **2015**, *27* (15), 2507–2514.
- (34) Monz, S.; Tschöpe, A.; Birringer, R. Magnetic Properties of Isotropic and Anisotropic CoFe₂O₄-Based Ferrogels and Their Application as Torsional and Rotational Actuators. *Phys. Rev. E Stat. Nonlin. Soft Matter Phys.* **2008**, *78* (2), 021404.
- (35) Gu, Y.; Kornev, K. G. Alignment of Magnetic Nanorods in Solidifying Films. *Part. Part. Syst. Charact.* **2013**, *30* (11), 958–963.
- (36) Si, J.-C.; Xing, Y.; Peng, M.-L.; Zhang, C.; Buske, N.; Chen, C.; Cui, Y.-L. Solvothermal Synthesis of Tunable Iron Oxide Nanorods and Their Transfer from Organic Phase to Water Phase. *CrystEngComm* **2014**, *16* (4), 512–516.
- (37) Brito-Silva, A. M.; Sobral-Filho, R. G.; Barbosa-Silva, R.; de Araújo, C. B.; Galembeck, A.; Brolo, A. G. Improved Synthesis of Gold and Silver Nanoshells. *Langmuir* **2013**, *29* (13), 4366–4372.
- (38) Rodrigo, I.; Castellanos-Rubio, I.; Garaio, E.; Arriortua, O. K.; Insausti, M.; Orue, I.; García, J. Á.; Plazaola, F. Exploring the Potential of the Dynamic Hysteresis Loops via High Field, High Frequency and Temperature Adjustable AC Magnetometer for Magnetic Hyperthermia Characterization. *Int. J. Hyperth.* **2020**, *37* (1), 976–991.
- (39) Li, N.; Huang, G.-W.; Shen, X.-J.; Xiao, H.-M.; Fu, S.-Y. Controllable Fabrication and Magnetic-Field Assisted Alignment of Fe₃O₄-Coated Ag Nanowires via a Facile Co-Precipitation Method. *J. Mater. Chem. C* **2013**, *1* (32), 4879–4884.
- (40) Sun, H.; Chen, B.; Jiao, X.; Jiang, Z.; Qin, Z.; Chen, D. Solvothermal Synthesis of Tunable Electroactive Magnetite Nanorods by Controlling the Side Reaction. *J. Phys. Chem. C* **2012**, *116* (9), 5476–5481.
- (41) Das, R.; Alonso, J.; Nemati Porshokouh, Z.; Kalappattil, V.; Torres, D.; Phan, M.-H.; Garaio, E.; García, J. Á.; Sanchez Llamazares, J. L.; Srikanth, H. Tunable High Aspect Ratio Iron Oxide Nanorods for Enhanced Hyperthermia. *J. Phys. Chem. C* **2016**, *120* (18), 10086–10093.
- (42) Dar, M. I.; Shivashankar, S. A. Single Crystalline Magnetite, Maghemite, and Hematite Nanoparticles with Rich Coercivity. *RSC Adv.* **2014**, *4* (8), 4105–4113.
- (43) Schwaminger, S. P.; Bauer, D.; Fraga-García, P.; Wagner, F. E.; Berensmeier, S. Oxidation of Magnetite Nanoparticles: Impact on Surface and Crystal Properties. *CrystEngComm* **2017**, *19* (2), 246–255.
- (44) Phonthammachai, N.; Kah, J. C. Y.; Jun, G.; Sheppard, C. J. R.; Olivo, M. C.; Mhaisalkar, S. G.; White, T. J. Synthesis of Contiguous Silica-Gold Core-Shell Structures: Critical Parameters and Processes. *Langmuir* **2008**, *24* (9), 5109–5112.
- (45) Otoufi, M. K.; Shahtahmasebebi, N.; Kompany, A.; Goharshadi, E. A Systematic Growth of Gold Nanoseeds on Silica for Silica@Gold Core-Shell Nanoparticles and Investigation of Optical Properties. *Int. J. Nano Dimens.* **2014**, *5* (6), 525–531.
- (46) Yu, H.; Chen, M.; Rice, P. M.; Wang, S. X.; White, R. L.; Sun, S. H. Dumbbell-like Bifunctional Au-Fe₃O₄

- Nanoparticles. *Nano Lett.* **2005**, *5* (2), 379–382.
- (47) Gatel, C.; Snoeck, E. Epitaxial Growth of Au and Pt on Fe₃O₄(111) Surface. *Surf. Sci.* **2007**, *601* (4), 1031–1039.
- (48) Ke, Y. J.; Qin, X. D.; Zhang, Y. C.; Li, H.; Li, R.; Yuan, J. L.; Yang, X.; Ding, S. M. In Vitro Study on Cytotoxicity and Intracellular Formaldehyde Concentration Changes after Exposure to Formaldehyde and Its Derivatives. *Hum. Exp. Toxicol.* **2014**, *33* (8), 822–830.
- (49) Lesiak, B.; Rangam, N.; Jiricek, P.; Gordeev, I.; Tóth, J.; Kövér, L.; Mohai, M.; Borowicz, P. Surface Study of Fe₃O₄ Nanoparticles Functionalized With Biocompatible Adsorbed Molecules. *Front. Chem.* **2019**, *7*, 642.
- (50) Alphantéry, E. Light-Interacting Iron-Based Nanomaterials for Localized Cancer Detection and Treatment. *Acta Biomater.* **2021**, *124*, 50–71.
- (51) Wicklein, B.; Kocjan, A.; Salazar-Alvarez, G.; Carosio, F.; Camino, G.; Antonietti, M.; Bergström, L. Thermally Insulating and Fire-Retardant Lightweight Anisotropic Foams Based on Nanocellulose and Graphene Oxide. *Nat. Nanotechnol.* **2015**, *10* (3), 277–283.
- (52) Walters, C. M.; Matharu, G. K.; Hamad, W. Y.; Lizundia, E.; MacLachlan, M. J. Chiral Nematic Cellulose Nanocrystal/Germania and Carbon/Germania Composite Aerogels as Supercapacitor Materials. *Chem. Mater.* **2021**, *33* (13), 5197–5209.
- (53) Liu, Y.; Sui, Y.; Liu, C.; Liu, C.; Wu, M.; Li, B.; Li, Y. A Physically Crosslinked Polydopamine/Nanocellulose Hydrogel as Potential Versatile Vehicles for Drug Delivery and Wound Healing. *Carbohydr. Polym.* **2018**, *188*, 27–36.
- (54) Rotjanasuworapong, K.; Thummarungsan, N.; Lerdwijitjarud, W.; Sirivat, A. Facile Formation of Agarose Hydrogel and Electromechanical Responses as Electro-Responsive Hydrogel Materials in Actuator Applications. *Carbohydr. Polym.* **2020**, *247*, 116709.
- (55) Ghebremedhin, M.; Seiffert, S.; Vilgis, T. A. Physics of Agarose Fluid Gels: Rheological Properties and Microstructure. *Curr. Res. Food Sci.* **2021**, *4*, 436–448.
- (56) Cuomo, F.; Cofelice, M.; Lopez, F. Rheological Characterization of Hydrogels from Alginate-Based Nanodispersion. *Polymers* **2019**, *11* (2), 259.
- (57) Guvendiren, M.; Lu, H. D.; Burdick, J. A. Shear-Thinning Hydrogels for Biomedical Applications. *Soft Matter* **2012**, *8* (2), 260–272.
- (58) Fan, D.-Y.; Tian, Y.; Liu, Z.-J. Injectable Hydrogels for Localized Cancer Therapy. *Front. Chem.* **2019**, *7*, 675.
- (59) Shin, M.; Song, K. H.; Burrell, J. C.; Cullen, D. K.; Burdick, J. A. Injectable and Conductive Granular Hydrogels for 3D Printing and Electroactive Tissue Support. *Adv. Sci.* **2019**, *6* (20), 1901229.
- (60) Dimatteo, R.; Darling, N. J.; Segura, T. In Situ Forming Injectable Hydrogels for Drug Delivery and Wound Repair. *Adv. Drug Deliv. Rev.* **2018**, *127*, 167–184.
- (61) Watt, J.; Bleier, G. C.; Romero, Z. W.; Hance, B. G.; Bierner, J. A.; Monson, T. C.; Huber, D. L. Gram Scale Synthesis of Fe/Fe_xO_y Core–Shell Nanoparticles and Their Incorporation into Matrix-Free Superparamagnetic Nanocomposites. *J. Mater. Res.* **2018**, *33* (15), 2156–2167.
- (62) Feng, B.; Hong, R. Y.; Wang, L. S.; Guo, L.; Li, H. Z.; Ding, J.; Zheng, Y.; Wei, D. G. Synthesis of

- Fe₃O₄/APTES/PEG Diacid Functionalized Magnetic Nanoparticles for MR Imaging. *Colloids Surfaces A Physicochem. Eng. Asp.* **2008**, *328* (1), 52–59.
- (63) Goya, G. F.; Berquó, T. S.; Fonseca, F. C.; Morales, M. P. Static and Dynamic Magnetic Properties of Spherical Magnetite Nanoparticles. *J. Appl. Phys.* **2003**, *94* (5), 3520–3528.
- (64) Mandawala, C.; Chebbi, I.; Durand-Dubief, M.; Le Fèvre, R.; Hamdous, Y.; Guyot, F.; Alphanbéry, E. Biocompatible and Stable Magnetosome Minerals Coated with Poly-L-Lysine, Citric Acid, Oleic Acid, and Carboxy-Methyl-Dextran for Application in the Magnetic Hyperthermia Treatment of Tumors. *J. Mater. Chem. B* **2017**, *5* (36), 7644–7660.
- (65) Gandia, D.; Gandarias, L.; Rodrigo, I.; Robles-García, J.; Das, R.; Garaio, E.; García, J. Á.; Phan, M.-H.; Srikanth, H.; Orue, I.; Alonso, J.; Muela, A.; Fdez-Gubieda, M. L. Unlocking the Potential of Magnetotactic Bacteria as Magnetic Hyperthermia Agents. *Small* **2019**, *15* (41), 1902626.
- (66) Boal, A. K.; Frankamp, B. L.; Uzun, O.; Tuominen, M. T.; Rotello, V. M. Modulation of Spacing and Magnetic Properties of Iron Oxide Nanoparticles through Polymer-Mediated “Bricks and Mortar” Self-Assembly. *J. Phys. Chem B* **2003**, *107*, 3252–3256.
- (67) Ding, X.; Liow, C. H.; Zhang, M.; Huang, R.; Li, C.; Shen, H.; Liu, M.; Zou, Y.; Gao, N.; Zhang, Z.; Li, Y.; Wnag, Q.; Li, S.; Jiang, J. Surface Plasmon Resonance Enhanced Light Absorption and Photothermal Therapy in the Second Near-Infrared Window. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2014**, *136* (44), 15684–15693.
- (68) Bashkatov, A. N.; Genina, E. A.; Kochubey, V. I.; Tuchin, V. V. Optical Properties of Human Skin, Subcutaneous and Mucous Tissues in the Wavelength Range from 400 to 2000 Nm. *J. Phys. D. Appl. Phys.* **2005**, *38* (15), 2543–2555.
- (69) Espinosa, A.; Silva, A. K. A.; Sánchez-Iglesias, A.; Grzelczak, M.; Péchoux, C.; Desboeufs, K.; Liz-Marzán, L. M.; Wilhelm, C. Cancer Cell Internalization of Gold Nanostars Impacts Their Photothermal Efficiency In Vitro and In Vivo: Toward a Plasmonic Thermal Fingerprint in Tumoral Environment. *Adv. Healthc. Mater.* **2016**, *5*, 1040–1048.
- (70) Freddi, S.; Sironi, L.; D’Antuono, R.; Morone, D.; Donà, A.; Cabrini, E.; D’Alfonso, L.; Collini, M.; Pallavicini, P.; Baldi, G.; Maggioni, D.; Chirico, G. A Molecular Thermometer for Nanoparticles for Optical Hyperthermia. *Nano Lett.* **2013**, *13* (5), 2004–2010.

Table of Contents (TOC)

